

On Finding Integer Solutions to the Homogeneous Cone

$$x^2 + (k^2 + 2k)y^2 = (k + 1)^4 z^2$$

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published online: 20 July 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Name J. Shanthi</p>	<p>This paper aims at determining non-zero distinct integer solutions to the homogeneous cone given by $x^2 + (k + 2k)y^2 = (k + 1)^4 z^2$. A few interesting properties between the solutions are presented.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Homogeneous cone ,Ternary quadratic ,Integer solutions</p>	

INTRODUCTION

The subject of quadratic Diophantine equations has a rich variety of fascinating problems. The homogeneous or non-homogeneous quadratic equations with three unknowns are rich in variety. For an extensive review of sizable literature

and various problems, one may refer [1-14].This paper concerns with yet another interesting homogeneous ternary quadratic Diophantine equation given by $x^2 + (k + 2k)y^2 = (k + 1)^4 z^2$ for determining its distinct integer solutions.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

The ternary quadratic equation representing homogeneous cone under consideration is $x^2 + (k^2 + 2k)y^2 = (k + 1)^4 z^2$ (1)The introduction of the linear transformations $x = X + (k^2 + 2k)T, y = X - T$ (2)in (1) leads to $X^2 + (k^2 + 2k)T^2 = (k + 1)^2 z^2$ (3)Assume $z = a^2 + (k + 2k)b^2$ (4) Write $(k + 1)^2$ on the R.H.S. of (3) as $(k + 1)^2 = (1 + i\sqrt{k^2 + 2k})(1 - i\sqrt{k^2 + 2k})$ (5)Substituting (4) and (5) in (3) and employing the method of factorization ,the corresponding values of X, T obtained through equating the rational and irrational parts are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= a^2 - (k^2 + 2k)b^2 - 2(k^2 + 2k)ab, \\ T &= a^2 - (k^2 + 2k)b^2 + 2ab \end{aligned}$$

In view of (2), it is seen that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &= (k + 1)^2 a^2 - (k^2 + 2k)(k + 1)^2 b^2, \\ y &= -2ab(k + 1)^2 \end{aligned} \right\} (6)$$

Thus, (4) and (6) represent the integer solutions to (1).

PROPERTIES

- i) $X + y$ is expressed as difference of two squares
- ii) x is a perfect square when $a = (k^2 + 2k)p^2 + q^2, b = 2pq$
- iii) z is a perfect square when $a = (k^2 + 2k)p^2 - q^2, b = 2pq$

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- iv) The members of the triple $(x, (k+1)^2 a^2, (k+1)^2 z)$ form an Arithmetic progression
- v) z is a cubical integer when $a = A(A^2 + (k+2k)B^2), b = B(A^2 + (k+2k)B^2)$
- vi) Each of the following expressions is a nasty number $3(x + (k+1)^2 z), 3(k+1)^2 (z + 2b^2) - 3x$. Albeit tacitly, there are other sets of integer solutions to (1) that are illustrated below:

Set 1: Write (3) as $(k + 1)^2 z^2 - (k^2 + 2k)T^2 = X^2$ (7) Assume $X = (k + 1)^2 a^2 - (k^2 + 2k) b^2$ (8)

Using (8) in (7) and applying the method of factorization, define $(k + 1)z + \sqrt{k^2 + 2k} T = ((k + 1)a + \sqrt{k^2 + 2k} b)^2$ (9)

Equating the rational and irrational parts in (9) and replacing b by $(k + 1)B$, the corresponding integer solutions to (1) after some algebra are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (k + 1)^4 a^2 - (k^2 + 2k)(k + 1)^2 (B - a)^2, \\ y &= (k + 1)^2 \left[(a - B)^2 - (k + 1)^2 B^2 \right], \\ z &= (k + 1)a^2 + (k^2 + 2k)(k + 1)B^2 \end{aligned}$$

Set 2:

Rewrite (7) as $(k + 1)^2 z^2 - (k^2 + 2k)T^2 = X^2 * 1$ (10) Write 1 on the R.H.S. of (10) as

$$1 = (k + 1 + \sqrt{k^2 + 2k})(k + 1 - \sqrt{k^2 + 2k}) \quad (11)$$

Substituting (8) & (11) in (10) and following the procedure as above, the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \left[(k^2 + 2k)b + (k + 1)^2 a \right]^2 - (k^2 + 2k)b^2, \\ y &= -2(k + 1)^2 a b - 2(k^2 + 2k)b^2, \\ z &= (k^2 + 2k)(a + b)^2 + a^2 \end{aligned}$$

Set 3:

Write (3) in the form of ratios as

$$\frac{(k + 1)z + X}{kT} = \frac{(k + 2)T}{(k + 1)z - X} = \frac{P}{Q}, Q \neq 0 \quad (12)$$

Which is equivalent to the system of double equations

$$\begin{aligned} QX - kPT + (k + 1)Qz &= 0, \\ PX + (k + 2)QT - (k + 1)Pz &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Employing the method of cross-multiplication and using (2), the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are found to be

$$\begin{aligned} x &= k(k + 1)^3 P^2 - (k + 1)(k + 2)(Q - kP)^2, \\ y &= (k + 1)(kP^2 - (k + 2)Q^2 - 2PQ), \\ z &= (k + 2)Q^2 + kP^2 \end{aligned}$$

Note: One may write (3) in the form of ratios as $\frac{(k + 1)z + X}{(k + 2)T} = \frac{kT}{(k + 1)z - X} = \frac{P}{Q}, Q \neq 0$

The repetition of the above process leads to a different set of integer solutions Remark: In addition to (2), on introducing the following linear transformations $x = X - (k^2 + 2k)T, y = X + T$, different sets of integer solutions to (1) are obtained.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, an attempt has been made to obtain non-zero distinct integer solutions to the considered homogeneous cone. To conclude, one may search for the integral solutions

to the other choices of homogeneous or non-homogeneous cones.

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